

[white paper]

Diamond Open Access

[awaiting peer review]

Intersection of Open Sets in the Reals

Open Mathematics Collaboration*[†]

August 28, 2023

Abstract

We demonstrate that while the intersection of a finite number of open sets in $\mathbb{R}$ remains open in $\mathbb{R}$, the same cannot be universally said for intersections involving an infinite number of open sets. An illustrative example is presented to highlight this distinction.

keywords: finite and infinite intersections of open sets in reals, topology

The most updated version of this white paper is available at

<https://osf.io/4kjdq/download>

<https://zenodo.org/record/8290012>

Introduction

1. [1–4]
2. $\mathbb{N} = \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$; $\mathbb{Z}^+ = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$
3. $A, B, C :=$ sets
4. $\vdash$ means its left side proves its right side

*All authors with their affiliations appear at the end of this white paper.

[†]Corresponding author: mplobo@uft.edu.br | **Open Mathematics Collaboration**

5. $(\mathcal{A} := \mathcal{B}) \equiv (\mathcal{A} \text{ is defined by } \mathcal{B})$
6. $(x =_{\ell} y) \equiv (\text{let } x \text{ be } y)$
7. $(xR_{\ell}A) \equiv (\text{let } xRA); \quad R := \text{binary relation}$
8. $\square := \text{qed, i.e., the theorem was proved}$
9. $(x \in A, B) \equiv ((x \in A) \wedge (x \in B))$
10. $(X \subseteq A, B) \equiv ((X \subseteq A) \wedge (X \subseteq B))$

Intersection of Two Open Sets in $\mathbb{R}$

11. Theorem

$$A \cap B \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$$

12. $A, B := \text{open sets in } \mathbb{R}$

13. Definitions

14.

$$(a, b) = \{x \in X \mid a < x < b\}$$

15.

$$\mathcal{X} := \text{open set in } Y$$

$$(i) \mathcal{X} \subseteq Y$$

$$(ii) \forall x \in \mathcal{X}, \exists (a, b) : x \in (a, b) \subseteq \mathcal{X}$$

16. $X, Y := \text{sets}$

17. $(a, b) := \text{open interval in } X$

18. Proof

19. $A, B =_{\ell} \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$

20. $x \in_{\ell} A \cap B$ arbitrary
21. $x \in A, B$
22. $A \equiv \text{open} \vdash \exists(a, b) : x \in (a, b) \subseteq A$
23. $B \equiv \text{open} \vdash \exists(c, d) : x \in (c, d) \subseteq B$
24. $C =_{\ell} (a, b) \cap (c, d)$
25. $x \in (a, b), (c, d) \vdash x \in C$
26. Lemma: $(a, b) \cap (c, d) \equiv \emptyset \vee \underline{\text{open interval in } \mathbb{R}}$.
27. (24, 25, 26) $\vdash C \equiv \text{open interval in } \mathbb{R}$
28. Lemma: $A \cap B \subseteq A$.
29. Lemma: $\cap$ is commutative, i.e., $A \cap B = B \cap A$.
30. $x \in (a, b) \subseteq A; x \in (c, d) \subseteq B; C = (a, b) \cap (c, d); A \cap B \subseteq A \vdash C \subseteq A, B$
31. Lemma: $C \subseteq A, B \rightarrow C \subseteq A \cap B$.
32. (30, 31) $\vdash C \subseteq A \cap B$
33. x arbitrary, (15, 20, 27, 32) $\vdash C \subseteq A \cap B, \forall x \in C, \exists(a, b) : x \in (a, b) \subseteq C \vdash A \cap B \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$ □

Intersection of Finite Open Sets in $\mathbb{R}$

34. [1]
35. Theorem
- $$\bigcap_{i=1}^n A_i \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$$
36. $A_i := \text{open sets in } \mathbb{R}$

37. $\bigcap A_i :=$ arbitrary intersection of A_i

38. Proof

39. For just one open set A ($n = 1$) in $\mathbb{R}$, we have $A \cap A = A$, which is open.

40. We will prove theorem (35) using the Principle of Induction.

41. Theorem (11) proves the base case ($n = 2$).

42. Let's proceed to the inductive step.

43. Induction Hypothesis:

$$\bigcap_{i=1}^k A_i \text{ is open in } \mathbb{R}.$$

44. We will prove

$$\bigcap_{i=1}^{k+1} A_i \text{ is open in } \mathbb{R}.$$

45. To prove (44), we need $k + 1$ sets.

46. It is convenient to create a family that contains $k + 1$ sets.

47. Let X be the set of $k + 1$ open sets in $\mathbb{R}$,

$$X = \{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_k, A\}.$$

48. Let

$$B = \bigcap_{i=1}^k A_i = A_1 \cap A_2 \cap \dots \cap A_k.$$

49. Hence, B is the intersection of all elements of X except A .

50. (43, 49) $\vdash$ B is an open set in $\mathbb{R}$.

51. (41, 47, 50) $\vdash$ $A \cap B$ is an open set in $\mathbb{R}$.

52. Therefore, we have proved that

$$\bigcap_{i=1}^{k+1} A_i$$

is an open set in $\mathbb{R}$.

□

Intersection of Infinite Open Sets in $\mathbb{R}$

53. [1]

54. Theorem

$$\bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i \equiv \neg \square \text{ open in } \mathbb{R}$$

55. $A_i :=$ open sets in $\mathbb{R}$

56. $\bigcap A_i :=$ arbitrary intersection of A_i

57. $\neg \square :=$ not necessarily

58. Proof

59. Let $X = \{(0, 1 + \frac{1}{n}) \mid n \in \mathbb{Z}^+\}$.

60. $\bigcap X = (0; 2) \cap (0; 1, 5) \cap (0; 1, 333\dots) \cap (0; 1, 25) \cap \dots \cap (0, 1 + \frac{1}{n}) \cap \dots$

61. Observe that for $n_1 < n_2$, we have $1 + \frac{1}{n_1} > 1 + \frac{1}{n_2}$.

62. From (61), since we are intersecting infinite open intervals and the second term on the right of the interval ($1/n$) is decreasing as n increases, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \bigcap X &= (0, 2) \cap (0, 1.5) \cap (0, 1.333\dots) \cap (0, 1.25) \cap \dots \\ &\quad \dots \cap \left(0, 1 + \frac{1}{n}\right) \cap \dots = (0, 1] \cup \left(0, \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n}\right) \\ &= (0, 1] \cup (0, 0) \\ &= (0, 1] \cup \emptyset, \text{ since } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

63. In (62), the addition between 1 and $\frac{1}{n}$ was converted (without loss of generality) into a union of intervals.

64. Hence,

$$\bigcap X = (0, 1].$$

□

Final Remarks

65. Throughout this paper, we've explored the intricate nature of intersecting infinite open sets within the real number system. The provided proofs underscore the subtle distinctions between finite and infinite intersections, a theme that resonates throughout many areas of mathematics.

66. The example utilizing the sequence of intervals converging to a single point is particularly enlightening, highlighting that the intersection of an infinite number of open intervals in $\mathbb{R}$ need not always be open. This result offers a cautionary note to mathematicians: our intuitive sense of infinity, particularly in the context of topology, can often lead to counterintuitive outcomes.

67. Furthermore, the use of the Principle of Induction has been instrumental in establishing the foundational steps of the proof. This serves as a testament to the power of this mathematical tool in elucidating complex concepts.

68. In future work, it would be valuable to delve deeper into other sequences of sets in $\mathbb{R}$ and their topological properties. This could potentially unveil other intriguing and unexpected results.

69. For educators in pure mathematics and theoretical physics, it's essential to illuminate these subtleties for students, as they underpin a vast array of more advanced mathematical concepts.

Open Invitation

Review, add content, and co-author this white paper [5,6].

*Join the **Open Mathematics Collaboration**.*

Send your contribution to mplobo@uft.edu.br.

Supplementary files

The **latex file** for this *white paper* together with other *supplementary files* are available in [7,8].

How to cite this paper?

<https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/4kjdq>

<https://zenodo.org/record/8290012>

Acknowledgements

+ **Center for Open Science**

<https://cos.io>

+ **Open Science Framework**

<https://osf.io>

+ **Zenodo**

<https://zenodo.org>

+ **OpenAI (GPT-4)**

<https://chat.openai.com>

Agreement

All authors agree with [6].

License

CC-By Attribution 4.0 International [4]

References

- [1] Warner, Steve. *Topology for Beginners*. GET 800, 2019.
<https://books.google.com/books?id=pNAvxQEACAAJ>
- [2] Lobo, Matheus P. “Theorems in Topology.” *OSF Preprints*, 21 Feb. 2022. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/zm56w>
- [3] Lobo, Matheus P. “Proofs of Theorems in Topology.” *OSF Preprints*, 7 June 2022. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/wn24y>
- [4] CC. Creative Commons. *CC-By Attribution 4.0 International*.
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>
- [5] Lobo, Matheus P. “Microarticles.” *OSF Preprints*, 28 Oct. 2019.
<https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ejrct>
- [6] Lobo, Matheus P. “Simple Guidelines for Authors: Open Journal of Mathematics and Physics.” *OSF Preprints*, 15 Nov. 2019.
<https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/fk836>
- [7] Lobo, Matheus P. “Open Journal of Mathematics and Physics (OJMP).” *OSF*, 21 Apr. 2020. <https://osf.io/6hzyp/files>
- [8] <https://zenodo.org/record/8290012>

The Open Mathematics Collaboration

Matheus Pereira Lobo (lead author, mplobo@uft.edu.br)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4554-1372>

Eriangra Oliveira dos Santos

Luiz Fernando Lima Barros

Federal University of Northern Tocantins (Brazil)